

TIME AS A PROGRAMMED DETERMINISTIC IDENTITY IN THE ARENA OF RANDOMNESS WITH APPLICATION TO SPATIAL DIVERGENCE

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ABSTRACT

This paper is an extension of my previous paper published in 'Zenodo' as "Computation of the loops of time travel with The detailed analysis of The Mandela Effect, 2-Time Dimensions, Death Loop, Merging of Parallel World, Teleportation and the Observable nature of the Physical Reality", 2020. I have introduced a special wavefunction relating to time as 'exponential wavefunction' which predicts the time as numbers and if we plot the numbers then there is a total randomness in them. Like, the velocity of different objects in this universe, the number of computations that gets evolved with time, the absolute uncertainty in weather prediction, the waves of oceans, the symphony of primes, the collision of two binary stars associated with the travelling of gravitational waves in different directions of varying magnitude over time, the numbers in the day to day events like the lottery tickets, share markets, the number of persons born and died in a single day, the amount of accidents occurs, the numbers of galaxies evolving thereby generating new stars and abolish old ones.... Each and everything is a number and if we studied these numbers carefully, then we will find a specific pattern associated with these numbers. This specific patterns although appears 'randomness' at first is usually a byproduct of 'determinism' which means in every numbers associated in the past there exists a relation to every numbers associated in the future with present being their superposition. This means what we are experiencing now are just the 'superposition of the Past and Future in a specific order or patterns' but sadly to say we as a human being are unaware of this patterns. If there are patterns and orders in the randomness as associated with time, then there must be some form of commons between these numbers, there must be something very similar to all the patterns and we humans are too fooled to find the commons between them. If the commons can be found, then there will be nothing as a surprise, we can predict each and every events in time with respect to certain events that we are concerned of. This indicates that every graphing pattern of numbers shows us a sense of 'causality' between them. This causality is the present which is the connecting link between the events which are causes in the past to the events which are effects in the future. This causal relationship is everywhere, at every point in the world and with this concept we can enter into the world of 'determinism'.... According to quantum theory 'information is conserved' that means 'information' can't be created or destroyed but what I mean by this is that information unfolds or evolves with time. The more the time passes, the more the past information unfolds and this paved the way for the deterministic universe. Everything has been there in past and everything will be there in future, all happening at the same places but in different times. Nothing new is created in course of time and nothing old is destroyed. What happens is that information unfolds at the very onset of the arrival of the current time. By means of determination, we can pave that every mapping from past to future happens for a reason and that mapping is of two types as classified by 'topology'... the 'bijective' mapping for day to day events and the 'surjective' mapping for the travelers in time. These two mappings preserve the information's which arises as a subset of time. Now the main ingredient of time is that it has been programmed, ever timeline or worldline at the onset of journey is being programmed till the end in a 'deterministic' way that that program is done by an agent of nature which we will introduce in this paper.

METHODOLOGY AND INTERPRETATION

An agent is an inert agent of pre-deterministic nature that allows the time to program against itself by means of a mapping from Past to Future. This mapping is done in the form of 'bijection' which we will see below.

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Here, there exist two sets.... *SET X* and *SET Y* which denotes 'past' and 'future' respectively. Event 'A' in past is mapped against event '1' in future. Similarly event 'B' to '2' and event 'C' to '3' is being mapped according to this image. This mapping is in respect to the worldline of a normal person (not a time traveler) in the spatial coordinates. Speaking mathematically...

$$\{A, B, C \dots\} \in SET X \text{ and } \{1,2,3 \dots\} \in SET Y$$

Or,

$$(A) = 1, F(B) = 2, F(C) = 3 \text{ where } F = X \rightarrow Y$$

In each of these functions (*F*) there exists an additive property of 'Superposition' such that there exists a *SET Z* which has the following property...

$$SET Z = \{ F(A, B, C \dots) = (1,2,3 \dots) \mid \{A, B, C \dots\} \text{ of } X \rightarrow \{1,2,3 \dots\} \text{ of } Y \}$$

This *SET Z* is the Present or the notion of 'PRESENT TIME'...

Here, as a person moves from A to 1, there exists a mutual string attached to the 'element A' which preserves the notion of space from 'A to 1' or "B to 2" or "C to 3"... This 'strings' has 2 parameters for preserving the 'Spatial Uniformity' as a **Set P = {(Right Accession, Declination), Gravitational Acceleration}**.

Here, we will now discuss why **Set P** is important. Suppose a person moves from 'Event A' in past to 'Event 1' in future then that means 'A' is correctly being mapped to '1' in time and space such that, 'A' is correctly being moved from Set X to Set Y in point '1' without any mistake, which means there is a 'Celestial Coordinate system and Gravitation' attached to 'A' that transfers it to 'B' so that 'A' from Set X goes correctly in Set B without ending in Mars as we have a 'Set P' as a condition attached to them which correctly determines the position of '1' with respect to 'A' in terms of *Right Accession, Declination and Gravitational Acceleration*. Of course a person can end up in Mars but that means he needs to alter the 'Strings' of the Program within *SET P* such that event '1' ends up in Mars related to event A in Earth but there must be a lot of intermediate events in between them, but for the ease of calculation, we will consider only the 'Initial and final events'. We can tell 'Set P' as the 'identifier' Set related to 'Set X' in Past and 'Set Y' in future.

SET P : X → Y ∃ P is Cont. or less Variable when compared to small distances and more when compared to large distances.

What do we actually mean by the above statement of logic? When 'Alice' moves from 'A' to '1' and if both are in *Earth* then Set P is Constant in terms of 'Celestial Coordinates' but not 'Gravitational Acceleration' as 'Gravitational Acceleration' changes with elevation in space and in this case "Set P is Less Variable" but if 'Alice' moves from 'A' to '1' where 'A' is in Earth and '1' is in Mars, "Set P is More Variable" when compared to 'large distances' as 'Both Celestial Coordinates and Gravitational acceleration' of Earth and Mars are hugely different.

Now, we will see the mapping of events in Time for a 'Time traveler' which is 'surjective' and will discuss why?

Here, everything is same as before except for the fact that, 'event 3' in Set Y has a different mapping from 'event C and D' in Set X. Here lies the fact, that a 'Time Traveler' can choose the right Possible 'Paths' to travel from Past to Future or there are 2 Time Travelers each at 'event C' and 'event D' but they wanted to go to the same event in Future as 'event 3'. That is why the mapping of a 'Time traveler' is different than a mapping of a normal person where the 'Agent' Programs his transformation from one event in

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past to a specified event in future via *Set P*, which shows that there is only 1 designated directions in between 2 events in case of a normal traveler rather than many possible paths of a time traveler. A time traveler is free to choose any possible paths whereas a normal person has only 1 degree of freedom or 1 paths that is destined to take him from past to future where future becomes present.

$C \rightarrow 3$ in case of Normal Person and C or $D \rightarrow 3$ in case of a Time Traveller

Now, we will delve into a more advanced concept by considering the below image.

[1]

RANDOMNESS increases the ENTROPY. When we are moving from future F-1 to a further future F-2, there is an increase in randomness and when in future F-3, the randomness increases. This denotes an increasing of the angle θ . The more the angle θ , the more the randomness which can be expressed in the following relationship...

$$\theta \propto \text{RANDOMNESS}$$

And this increases the *DETERMINISM* or the *CAUSAL CONNECTION* between *CAUSE* and *EFFECT* within a string of Randomness. This Programming which has been done by the Agent of Nature specifies the Deterministic logic where every event of Past are connected with every event of Future through a Pre-Destined Logic into the chaos of Randomness. Therefore, the relation is.... All the events are causally connected in this chaotic and random future. There is a specified pattern in the randomness, a synchronicity, a pattern connecting two distinct events in space-time.

REFERENCE

1. Schwarz, Rob "John Titor: The man with the machine", February 4, 2013 <https://www.strangerdimensions.com/2013/02/04/john-titor-the-man-with-the-machine/>

SUGGESTED READS

Deep Bhattacharjee, "Computation of the loops of time travel with The detailed analysis of The Mandela Effect, 2-Time Dimensions, Death Loop, Merging of Parallel World, Teleportation and the Observable nature of the Physical Reality", 2020, Zenodo.org.